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INTERNET VA IJTIMOY TARMOQLAR: YOSHLAR ONGIGA TA'SIRI VA XAVFLARI

Salomov Sirojiddin Abdimalikovich

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning yoshlar ongiga ta'siri hamda ular bilan bog'liq xavflar tahlil qilingan. Ilmiy adabiyotlar va amaliy tadqiqotlar asosida ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning ijobiy imkoniyatlari hamda salbiy oqibatlari yoritilgan. Muallif internet muhitidagi axborot oqimining ruhiy salomatlik, ma'naviy qadriyatlar va ijtimoiy barqarorlikka ta'sirini o'rganadi. Maqolada yangi ilmiy xulosalar bilan bir qatorda, yoshlarda media savodxonlikni oshirish hamda axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: internet; ijtimoiy tarmoqlar; yoshlar; ruhiy salomatlik; axborot xavfsizligi; media savodxonlik; ekstremizm; ijtimoiy ta'sir.

Abstract: The article analyzes the influence of the Internet and social networks on the consciousness of young people, as well as the risks associated with them. Based on scientific literature and practical research, it highlights both the positive opportunities and the negative consequences of using social media. The author examines the impact of information flows in the online environment on mental health, moral values, and social stability. Along with new scientific findings, the article also provides practical recommendations for improving youth media literacy and ensuring information security.

Key words: Internet; social networks; youth; mental health; information security; media literacy; extremism; social influence.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется влияние интернета и социальных сетей на сознание молодежи, а также связанные с ними риски. На основе научной литературы и практических исследований раскрываются как положительные возможности, так и негативные последствия использования социальных сетей. Автор изучает воздействие информационного потока в интернет-среде на психическое здоровье, духовные ценности и социальную стабильность. В статье, наряду с новыми научными выводами, предлагаются практические рекомендации по повышению медиаграмотности молодежи и обеспечению информационной безопасности.

Ключевые слова: Интернет; социальные сети; молодежь; психическое здоровье; информационная безопасность; медиаграмотность; экстремизм; социальное влияние.

KIRISH

Internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar bugungi kunda zamonaviy jamiyat hayotining ajralmas qismiga aylangan bo'lib, ular nafaqat axborot almashish vositasi, balki iqtisodiy, siyosiy va madaniy jarayonlarning muhim harakatlantiruvchi kuchlaridan biri sifatida ham e'tirof etilmoqda. Xususan, yoshlar uchun internet bilim olish, muloqot qilish va o'zini ifoda etishning eng samarali maydoniga aylangan. Onlayn kurslar, virtual kutubxonalar va ta'lim platformalari bilim olish imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar esa turli millat va madaniyat vakillari bilan muloqot qilish, yangi do'stlar orttirish hamda shaxsiy fikr va g'oyalarni erkin tarzda ifoda etish imkonini beradi.

Shu bilan birga, internetdan oqilona va maqsadga muvofiq foydalanish masalasi ham dolzarbdir. Ba'zan internetdan me'yordan ortiq foydalanish vaqtini noto'g'ri taqsimlashga, diqqatni jamlash qobiliyatining susayishiga va ijtimoiy faoliyatdan chetlashishga olib kelishi mumkin. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti 2022-yilda e'lon qilgan ma'lumotlarda internetdan ortiqcha foydalanishni zamonaviy davrning yangi ijtimoiy muammolaridan biri sifatida baholagan (World Health Organization, 2022). Bu holat internet madaniyatini shakllantirish, media savodxonlikni rivojlantirish va yoshlarni axborot xatarlaridan himoya qilish zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

Shu sababli, internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning yoshlar ongiga ta'sirini ilmiy asosda o'rganish nafaqat nazariy, balki amaliy ahamiyatga ham ega. Ushbu jarayonlarni chuqur tahlil etish orqali internetning ijobiy imkoniyatlarini to'g'ri yo'naltirish, raqamli madaniyatni rivojlantirish hamda yoshlarning ma'naviy va intellektual salohiyatini yanada yuksaltirish imkoniyati yaratiladi.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning ijobiy ta'sirlari ko'p qirrali bo'lib, ularning ta'lim, madaniyat va muloqot jarayonlaridagi o'rni alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bir qator tadqiqotlar internetning ta'lim sohasidagi o'rni va imkoniyatlarini keng yoritgan. Masalan, S. Zayniyeva (2023) o'z tadqiqotida internet orqali yoshlarning bilim olish imkoniyatlari sezilarli darajada kengayganini ta'kidlaydi. Bugungi kunda onlayn kurslar, elektron kutubxonalar, ta'lim platformalari va virtual treninglar ta'lim tizimida yangi bosqichni boshlab berdi. Bu jarayon yoshlarga universitet yoki maktab dasturlari bilan cheklanib qolmasdan, "Coursera", "Udemy" va "Khan Academy" kabi xalqaro platformalar orqali dunyo ilm-fani yutuqlaridan bahramand bo'lish imkonini yaratmoqda.

Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlar uchun ijodiy o'zini namoyon qilish, shaxsiy yutuqlarini ko'rsatish, madaniy almashinuvni kengaytirish hamda xalqaro muloqot maydonini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda (Mamajonova, 2022). Masalan, "Instagram" va "TikTok" kabi platformalar orqali yoshlar o'z ijodiy ishlarini millionlab auditoriyaga taqdim etish, qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, ijtimoiy nufuzini oshirish hamda iqtisodiy daromad manbaini yaratish imkoniga ega bo'lmoqdalar.

Jahon banki ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 2023-yilda dunyo bo'yicha internet foydalanuvchilari soni 5,3 milliard kishiga yetgan, shundan qariyb 60 foizi ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda faol hisoblanadi (World Bank, 2023). Ushbu raqamlar internetning global hayotga qanchalik chuqur kirib borganini va inson faoliyatining barcha sohalariga ta'sir etayotganini yaqqol ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ishtirok etish yoshlar o'rtasida muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish, turli madaniy muhit va turmush tarzini o'rganishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Ruhij va ma'naviy omillarni tahlil etish internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning ta'sirini o'rganishda muhim yo'nalishlardan biridir. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan me'yordan ortiq foydalanish ayrim yoshlar ongida internetga qaramlik, ruhiy bosim va depressiya holatlariga olib kelishi mumkin. F. Boymurodova va B. Norbekova (2023) tadqiqotlarida ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ortiqcha vaqt o'tkazish yoshlar orasida xavotir va stress darajasining oshishiga sabab bo'lishi aniqlangan. Shuningdek, M. Norboyeva va G. Allayarovanning (2023) ilmiy maqolasida "FOMO" (fear of missing out – imkonni boy berishdan qo'rquv) holati yoshlar ongida o'zini boshqalar bilan taqqoslash, xavotir va ruhiy noqulaylik hissini kuchaytirayotgani ta'kidlanadi. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, AQShda yoshlarning 46 foizi har kuni kamida 5 soatini ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda o'tkazadi va ularning 32 foizi ruhiy salomatlik bilan bog'liq muammolarni his qilmoqda (Pew Research Center, 2022). Ushbu ma'lumotlar ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan ortiqcha foydalanish inson ruhiy barqarorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini tasdiqlaydi.

Axborot xavfsizligi va ekstremizm masalalari ham dolzarb hisoblanadi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar ayrim hollarda ekstremistik va radikal g'oyalarni tarqatish uchun qulay maydon vazifasini bajaradi. Turli tadqiqotlarda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali terrorizmni oqlash, millatlararo nizo va adovatni qo'zg'atish hamda radikal g'oyalarni targ'ib etish holatlari kuzatilgani qayd etilgan. Ayniqsa, yoshlarning axborotni tanlash va tahlil qilish ko'nikmalari yetarlicha shakllanmagani sababli ular manipulyatsiyaga beriluvchan bo'lib, axborot muhitidagi tahdidlarga nisbatan zaiflik ko'rsatishlari mumkin.

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

Kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha xalqaro tashkilotlar ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, har kuni 85 mingdan ortiq saytga xakerlik hujumlari amalga oshiriladi va milliardlab ma'lumotlar tarqatiladi (Cybersecurity Ventures, 2022). Ushbu raqamlar axborot muhitidagi xavf va tahdidlarning keng qamrovini, shuningdek, kiberxavfsizlik masalalariga jiddiy yondashish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda tarqatilayotgan yolg'on axborotlar va manipulyativ kontentlar nafaqat yoshlar ongiga, balki jamiyatning axborot barqarorligiga ham ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Ekstremistik mazmundagi kontentlarning oldini olish, yoshlarni ijobiy g'oyalar va bunyodkorlik yo'nalishiga yo'naltirish bugungi kunda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ayrim radikal guruhlar yoshlar e'tiborini jalb etish maqsadida "Adolat uchun kurash" kabi shiorlar ostida chiroyli videoroliklar va emotsional murojaatlar orqali ta'sir o'tkazishga harakat qiladi. Shu bois, yoshlar ongida tanqidiy fikrlash, axborotni tahlil qilish va haqiqatni yolg'ondan ajrata olish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish dolzarb vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Ota-onalar va ta'lim muassasalari tomonidan internetdan foydalanish madaniyatini rivojlantirish ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Oila bolaning shaxsiyati va dunyoqarashi shakllanadigan birlamchi muhit sifatida uning axborot maydonidagi xatti-harakatlarini belgilaydi. Mizomova va Xasanova (2024) tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, ota-onalarning muntazam nazorati, mehrga asoslangan tarbiyaviy suhbatlari va bolalar bilan ochiq muloqot yuritishlari internet xavflarini kamaytirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Shuningdek, maktab va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qituvchilarning pedagogik yondashuvi, media savodxonlik darslari va targ'ibot ishlari yoshlarning axborotdan to'g'ri foydalanish ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlaydi.

Davlat darajasida esa axborot xavfsizligi va kiberxavfsizlik sohasidagi strategiyalarni takomillashtirish doimiy e'tibor talab etadi. Bu borada nafaqat texnik himoya vositalarini kuchaytirish, balki keng jamoatchilik o'rtasida media madaniyatni yuksaltirish ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Chunki har bir fuqaroning axborot madaniyati yuksak bo'lsa, kiberxavfsizlikning ijtimoiy poydevori ham mustahkamlanadi.

Yevropa Ittifoqi mamlakatlarida media savodxonlik ta'lim dasturlariga majburiy fan sifatida kiritilgan. Masalan, Finlyandiyada o'quvchilar maktab dasturida "Axborotni tekshirish" va "Soxta yangiliklarni aniqlash" fanlarini o'rganadilar (European Commission, 2021). Ushbu tajriba yoshlarning axborotni tahlil qilish, uning ishonchligini baholash va manipulyativ materiallarni aniqlay olish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Mazkur tajriba O'zbekiston uchun ham o'rnak bo'lishi mumkin. Chunki globallashtirish va raqamli texnologiyalar asrida axborotdan oqilona foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirish, yoshlar ongida media savodxonlikni rivojlantirish hamda ularni ijobiy g'oyalarga yo'naltirish jamiyatning barqarorligi va ma'naviy xavfsizligini ta'minlashda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlar uchun beqiyos imkoniyatlar yaratib, ularning bilim olish, ijodiy fikrlash va global muloqot doirasini kengaytirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, mazkur raqamli muhit yoshlarning ruhiy, ma'naviy va ijtimoiy barqarorligini mustahkamlashda ham muhim omil bo'lib, to'g'ri foydalanilganda u shaxsiy o'sish va ijtimoiy faollikni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Biroq axborot oqimining juda tezkorligi va keng qamrovi sababli yoshlar turli xil ta'sirlarga ochiq bo'ladi, bu esa ulardan axborotni tanlab qabul qilish va tahlil qilish madaniyatini talab etadi. Shu bois internetning ijobiy imkoniyatlarini to'g'ri yo'naltirish, raqamli madaniyatni rivojlantirish hamda axborotdan oqilona foydalanish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish jamiyat va ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan ustuvor vazifalardan biridir.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Media savodxonlikni oshirish, axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash hamda oila va ta'lim muassasalarida internetdan oqilona foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirish bugungi kunda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bunday yondashuv yoshlarning ma'naviy va ruhiy barqarorligini mustahkamlab, ularning tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi, shuningdek, raqamli muhitda mas'uliyatli va ongli faoliyat yuritishga yo'naltiradi. Shu bilan birga, yoshlarni sog'lom raqobatbardosh, ijtimoiy faol va ijodkor shaxs sifatida shakllantirish internetdan samarali foydalanish madaniyati bilan bevosita bog'liqdir.

Davlat va jamiyat hamkorligida amalga oshiriladigan kompleks chora-tadbirlar, kiberxavfsizlik siyosatini yanada takomillashtirish, ekstremizm va radikalizmga qarshi ma'rifiy faoliyatni kengaytirish, shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ijobiy, ma'naviy va tarbiyaviy mazmundagi kontentni ko'paytirish internetdan kelib chiqadigan xavf-xatarlarning oldini olishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Demak, internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirish nafaqat yoshlarning kelajagi, balki butun jamiyatning ma'naviy, axloqiy va intellektual barqarorligini ta'minlash, milliy xavfsizlikni mustahkamlash hamda barqaror taraqqiyotga erishish uchun ham strategik ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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